

AN EFFICIENT FINITE ELEMENT
FOR THICK LAMINATED AND SANDWICH BEAMS

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ABSTRACT

The analysis of thick laminated composite structures and sandwich structures should take into account the effects of transverse shear. However two main difficulties arise, i.e. the derivation of convenient theories taking into account the transverse effects and the derivation of efficient finite elements for numerical solutions. Whereas the Timoshenko theory provides a simple and rather efficient description of shear effects in homogeneous beam, its adaptation to heterogeneous beams need a proper computation of the transverse shear stiffness from the properties of the constitutive materials. Classical analyses using displacements hypotheses (strain energy) do not give convenient values for this transverse stiffness. A formula is established in the first part of the work to predict the shear stiffness based on the use of the complementary transverse shear energy. In the second part of the work, a new finite element for thick beams (homogeneous or heterogeneous) is derived. It uses shape functions based on exact close-form solution for thick beams in special cases. These shape functions, and consequently the elementary stiffness matrices and the elementary consistent loads, are equal to the corresponding quantities for classical beams plus corrective terms which involve a dimensionless factor vanishing when shear effects vanish. This provide a very significant improvement with respect to the previously available elements ; specially, it solves the so-called "locking phenomenon", which occurs when the span-to-depth ratio becomes high and is a major drawback of the other elements, and it gives very fast and accurate results for the analysis of composite beams.

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF A STRAIGHT BEAM WITH SHEAR

The basic equations of an elastic beam with shear (Timoshenko beam) are 1) the kinematics equations, 2) the equilibrium equations, and 3) the stress-strain relations :

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 K = \frac{d\psi}{dx} & \frac{dM}{dx} = Q & M = DK \\
 (1) & (2) & (3) \\
 \Gamma = \frac{dw}{dx} + \psi & \frac{dQ}{dx} + q = 0 & Q = d\Gamma
 \end{array}$$

where w is the deflection, ψ the rotation, K the generalized curvature, Γ the shear deformation, M the bending moment, Q the shear force, q the transverse load, while D and d are the bending and shear stiffnesses. The differences with the well-known Euler-Bernoulli equations lie

mainly in the shear stiffness. From a theoretical point of view, a first question arises in the computation of this quantity from the geometrical and material properties of the beam, the other point being to assess the effective influence of this shear stiffness. For a beam (or a part of beam) with length L , height H and width B , it is convenient to introduce the adimensional ratio :

$$a = \frac{12D}{dL^2} = \frac{E^*}{G^*} \left(\frac{H}{L}\right)^2$$

This ratio involves both geometrical and materials parameters (E^* and G^* are the equivalent Young's modulus and shear modulus, i.e. moduli of an equivalent homogeneous material giving the same stiffnesses as the ones of the real heterogeneous beam). It equals zero for very thin beams ($H/L \ll 1$) and beams with infinite shear stiffness ($d=\infty$, i.e. the classical Euler Bernoulli beam).

For a beam or a part of beam (extending from x_1 to x_2) loaded by couples and shear forces at its ends only ($q = 0$), an exact close-form solution can be derived, which is constant for Q , linear for M , quadratic for ψ and cubic for w . It contains 4 independent parameters, which can be chosen as the 4 values w_1, w_2, ψ_1, ψ_2 of the deflection and the rotation at the ends. After some computations, one finds :

$$\begin{aligned} w &= w_1 P_1^a(r) + w_2 P_2^a(r) - \psi_1 L R_1^a(r) - \psi_2 L R_2^a(r) \\ \psi &= -w_1 S_1^a(r)/L - w_2 S_2^a(r)/L + \psi_1 T_1^a(r) + \psi_2 T_2^a(r) \end{aligned}$$

where $r = (2x - x_1 - x_2)/L$ is the reduced abscissa, and the eight influence functions $P_1, P_2, R_1, R_2, S_1, S_2, T_1, T_2$ are polynomials given in the Appendix, depending on the ratio a .

This basic solution, previously given (although in a somewhat different form) by several Strength-of-Materials textbooks, has interesting characteristics. First, the influence function can be expressed as the sum of the influence functions of the Euler-Bernoulli beam (independent of a) and corrective terms with $a/(1+a)$ as a multiplier (see the Appendix). Consequently, they reduce to the Euler-Bernoulli influence functions when $a=0$, and, more generally, the solution reduces to the Euler-Bernoulli solution in that case. Also, the following relationship can be derived.:

$$\{F\} = [K_e^T] \{u\}$$

where :

$$\{F\} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_1 \\ M_1 \\ Q_2 \\ M_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -Q(-1) \\ -M(-1) \\ +Q(+1) \\ +M(+1) \end{bmatrix} \quad \{u\} = \begin{bmatrix} w_1 \\ \psi_1 \\ w_2 \\ \psi_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} w(-1) \\ \psi(-1) \\ w(+1) \\ \psi(+1) \end{bmatrix}$$

and the 4 x 4 stiffness matrix is:

$$K_e^T = \frac{D}{L^3(1+a)} \begin{bmatrix} 12 & -6L & -12 & -6L \\ -6L & (4+a)L^2 & 6L & (2-a)L^2 \\ -12 & 6L & 12 & 6L \\ -6L & (2-a)L^2 & 6L & (4+a)L^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Again, this stiffness matrix reduces to Euler-Bernoulli stiffness matrix when shear effects vanish. It can be used in the old classical matrix methods of structural mechanics and this provides exact solutions for the nodal variables.

DERIVATION OF SHEAR STIFFNESS

The correct estimate of the shear stiffness from the geometrical and material properties of the cross-section of the beam has been for years an important challenge. Even for homogeneous isotropic materials, problems arise from the classical analyses, for they use displacements as variables, which leads to models which are too stiff; this question is solved, or maybe eluded, by the use of shear correction factors.¹ However, for heterogeneous structures, an extra difficulty comes from the fact that displacement hypotheses cannot meet all the continuity requirements at the interfaces between layers, i.e. continuity of the displacement and continuity of the transverse stresses.² This problem can be solved by using the intermediate energy variational methods introduced by the author.^{2,3,4} However, for the estimate of the shear stiffness, these methods can be reduced to the complementary energy of the transverse shear. The derivation is summarized in the following.

The shear complementary energy per unit length is defined as :

$$\Phi_s = \frac{1}{2} \iint \tau^2 / G \, dS$$

in which τ is the transverse shear and G is the shear modulus, which can vary from point to point in the cross section.

A one-parameter modelization of the shear is introduced :

$$\tau^* = QF$$

in which $F = F(y,z)$ is a given function defined in the cross section with the following normalizing condition :

$$\iint F \, dS = 1$$

so that one gets :

$$Q = \iint \tau^* dS$$

i.e. Q stands for the shear force.

With this approximate shear, the energy per unit length reduces to :

$$\Phi_s^* = \frac{1}{2} \frac{Q^2}{d}$$

in which d is given by :

$$\frac{1}{d} = \frac{1}{2} \iint F^2 / G dS$$

The shear deformation can be obtained by derivation of the energy with respect to the shear force :

$$\Gamma = \frac{\partial \Phi_s^*}{\partial Q}$$

which gives finally :

$$Q = d\Gamma$$

The method is dependent on the choice of the function F(y,z). The simplest one is to use the parabolic distribution of the shear along the the thickness :

$$F_1 = \frac{3}{2B} \left[1 - \frac{4z^2}{H^2} \right]$$

It leads to the classical (5/6) value of the corrective shear factor for homogeneous beam and a material dependent factor for laminated beam. A special form for F, as in Ref.4, must be used for sandwich beam in order to get effective results. Generally, by modifying the function F, it is possible to adjust the value of d to other results, such as obtained by minimechanics.⁵

A FINITE ELEMENT FOR BEAM WITH SHEAR

For years, the finite element approach to structures sensitive to shear has used classical shape functions (of the Serendip isoparametric type), selected independently for the different variables (deflections and rotations). Even in the simple case of beams, it is well known that the derived elements have poor properties. Specially, they are very sensitive to the span-to-depth ratio. For thick beam, they behave almost conveniently, although they have a slow convergence (specially the two-node element). But for thin or very thin beams, they show deviating results (immoderately too stiff values), which is known as the locking phenomenon.⁶ Various explanations have been given to that,

based on the difference in strain energy between pure bending and shear, and numerical methods, such as the selective integration,⁷ have been proposed to improve the element behaviour. However, all these methods give the following form for the stiffness matrix :

$$[K] = D [B] + d [S]$$

or :

$$[K] = D ([B] + 12 [S] / aL^2)$$

in which the bending part B and the shear part S depend only on the length L of the element. The various derivations give various values for the shear part. However, it is clear that such a form cannot give good results when the shear stiffness d tends to infinity or when the adimensional ratio a vanishes (i.e. when the Timoshenko beam tends to the Euler-Bernoulli beam). Further, the comparison of the above form with the Strength-of-Materials stiffness matrix given in the previous paragraph emphasizes that no possibility exists to make the matrices equal using numerical tricks.

Keeping in view that, conversely, the Euler-Bernoulli beam finite elements perform excellently, the present work looked for a kind of extension of these elements. The solution to that is provided by the exact analysis presented in the previous part : as the Euler-Bernoulli influence functions are precisely the shape functions of these well-performing elements, it can be inferred that the shear beam influence functions could be used as shape functions for a shear beam element.

As it could have been guessed, it was found that, with such shape functions, the stiffness matrix of the element is exactly equal to the one of the above exact solution. It can be anticipated that such an element can be reduced to Euler-Bernoulli elements when the shear effects vanish or the span-to-depth ratio tends to infinity. This has been completely confirmed by numerical implementation and examples, which showed that exact solutions can be reproduced for any span-to-depth ratios. Further, consistent loads were derived from these shape functions and used in the finite element process with much success.

However, the use of these influence functions as shape functions raises questions. As they include a as a parameter, these functions depend on the material properties of the element. This has apparently never been used previously for finite elements. Although not explicitly allowed by reference textbooks on finite elements,^{8,9} it has no more been explicitly forbidden. Its success in the present case can establish its legitimacy. Finally, it should be pointed out that the parameter a in the shape functions is relative to the element itself and not to the beam, i.e. the length L and height H to be used are those of the considered element.

CONCLUSION

Two contributions to the analysis of homogeneous and heterogeneous (laminated or sandwich) thick beams were presented. An adjustable method for deriving the shear stiffness from the geometrical and material properties of the cross-section was derived from a partial complementary energy. Then, from a close-form solution, shape functions which are material dependent were induced. The finite element derived from them possesses an exact stiffness matrix and is not sensitive to

the locking phenomenon for high span-to-depth ratio. The extension of these results to plates and shells are currently studied.

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APPENDIX

Influence functions / shape functions for the Timoshenko beam :

$$P_1^a(r) = P_1^0(r) + \frac{2a}{1+a} p(r)$$

$$R_1^a(r) = R_1^0(r) + \frac{a}{1+a} p(r)$$

$$S_1^a(r) = S_1^0(r) + \frac{2a}{1+a} s(r)$$

$$T_1^a(r) = T_1^0(r) + \frac{a}{1+a} s(r)$$

$$P_2^a(r) = P_2^0(r) - \frac{2a}{1+a} p(r)$$

$$R_2^a(r) = R_2^0(r) + \frac{a}{1+a} p(r)$$

$$S_2^a(r) = S_2^0(r) - \frac{2a}{1+a} s(r)$$

$$T_2^a(r) = T_2^0(r) + \frac{a}{1+a} s(r)$$

where :

$$P_1^0(r) = + \frac{(1-r)^2(2+r)}{4}$$

$$R_1^0(r) = + \frac{(1-r)^2(1+r)}{8}$$

$$S_1^0(r) = - \frac{3(1-r^2)}{2}$$

$$T_1^0(r) = - \frac{(1-r)(1+3r)}{4}$$

$$P_2^0(r) = + \frac{(1+r)^2(2-r)}{4}$$

$$R_2^0(r) = - \frac{(1-r)(1+r)^2}{8}$$

$$S_2^0(r) = + \frac{3(1-r^2)}{2}$$

$$T_2^0(r) = - \frac{(1+r)(1-3r)}{4}$$

and :

$$p(r) = \frac{r(1-r^2)}{8}$$

$$s(r) = \frac{3(1-r^2)}{4}$$